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Research Article

COMPARISON OF THREE DIFFERENT PROCEDURES OF VARICOCELECTOMY IN PATIENTS OF INFERTILITY

Dr Naveed Sultan, Dr Muhammad Nadeem, Dr Abubaker

Institute of Kidney Diseases, PGMI Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to compare the consequences of three different procedures on the varicocelelectomy in patients suffering from infertility with the utilization of the varicoceles.

Methodology: There were total two hundred and eight patients with infertility (four hundred and forty-six varicoceles) who got for varicocelelectomy by an open inguinal procedure in ninety-two patients, laparoscopy in ninety-four patients & sub-inguinal microsurgeries in one hundred and twelve patients. We compared the all three procedures about intra-operative, initial & delayed parameters after surgery, alterations in the parameters of semen & rate of pregnancy. Average follow up duration of the patients was 21.0 ± 9.0 months with a range from four to thirty-five months.

Results: The surgery duration was much greater in the microscopic group of study. We compared the initial complications after surgery in all three groups. During the follow up period, no patient in the micro-surgical group found with hydrocele, whereas we observed that four out of 143 (2.80%) in the group of open procedure & eight out of 148 (5.40%) in the group of laparoscopy group, demonstrating an important disparity in the support of the microsurgery. The occurrence of the recurring varicoceles was much less in the micro-surgical group as compared to the other groups of open & laparoscopy (four out of 155 or 2.60% patients' vs sixteen out of 143 or 11.0% & twenty-five out of 148 or 17.0%, correspondingly). In comparison with the values before surgery in all groups the parameters of semen after surgery displayed advancement in the concentration of sperm, sperm's motility & morphology. The prevalence of the infertile patients with improved count of the sperm & their motility was very high in the group of micro-surgery. The rate of pregnancy was not much different in all the participants of each group.

Conclusions: The comparison of all 3 techniques showed that micro-surgical varicocelelectomy has high benefits as compared to the other methods as no formation of the hydrocele, very low occurrence of recurring varicocele and good improvement in the count & motility of the sperms.

KEY WORDS: Infertile, Micro-Surgery, Laparoscopy, Varicocelelectomy, Varicocele, Motility, Prevalence.

Corresponding author:**Dr.Naveed Sultan,**

Institute of Kidney Diseases, PGMI Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar

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INTRODUCTION:

Varicocele is available in 12.0% population of male gender & in about 25.0% males suffering from infertility [1]. The influence of the varicocele therapy associated with increased rate of pregnancy in the couple suffering from infertility is very provocative problem [2]. Different research works have displayed an important rise in the rate of pregnancy in the patients having treatment of varicocele [3]. But in opposition, meta-analysis of different works displays that there are no present proofs qualifying surgical treatment or radiological therapy for varicocele in men of the couples with infertility [4]. The findings of Evers & Collins [5] showed an impact on commendations of the EAUWGMI (European Association of Urology Working Group on Male Infertility) regarding therapy for the infertility of men [6].

But an American association was present with opposite views regarding this matter [7]. So, there was much controversy present in the recommendation of various associations. Due to the prevalence of these controversies, this prospective, randomized with a high proportion of the infertile patients carried out with clinically intense varicocele. The standard technique for varicocele therapy is other contentious problem. There are several methods which are in use. There are advantages & demerits of every procedure and various case works provided conflicting outcomes [8-13]. In this research work, we tried to overcome the

shortcomings of various past research works providing the comparison of the results of three very common procedures.

METHODOLOGY:

There were two hundred and ninety-eight patients with infertility (four hundred and forty-six medically palpable varicoceles) who experienced varicocelectomy in Institute of Kidney Diseases, Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar from May 2018 to May 2019. We performed 3 different procedures randomly, open method for ninety-two patients, laparoscopy in ninety-four patients & sub-inguinal micro-surgeries in one hundred and twelve patients. Table-1 shows the traits of patients & varicoceles in all the patients of three groups. Only single expert surgeon performed every method who had the at least of fifty methods before this surgery. The patients who underwent surgery by various surgeons and those having symptoms of other than infertility were not the part of this research work. All the patients gave their written consent to participate in the research work. Ethical committee of the institute gave the permission to conduct this research work. The different participants in the groups were due to the exclusion of some patients from those groups. We carried out at least two semen analysis in assessment before surgery. We also got the help of Doppler assistance to define the varicocele on ultra-sonography [14].

Table 1. Patient and Varicocele Characteristics

Characteristics	No. pts	No. Varicoceles	No. varicocele Side		Age		Range
			Lt	Bilat	Mean	± SD	
Open	92.0	143.0	41.0	51.0	34.0	7.80	22-59
Laparoscopic	94.0	148.0	40.0	54.0	33.0	7.90	20-53
Microscopic	112.0	155.0	69.0	43.0	34.0	6.60	22-55
p Value			0.700		0.800		

We used the standard techniques according to the prescribed prescription for the application of all three procedures. We evaluated the time of surgery, pain duration the surgery, need of analgesia, initial complications after surgery, stay in the hospital & time of recovery or return to routine activities. We used a special questionnaire for the evaluation of the pain having zero to six points. The average follows up duration was 21.0 ± 9.0 months. We compared the parameters of the semen before and after the surgery in every participant of all three groups. We elaborated the advancement or worsening in the parameters of semen as a higher than 20.0% alteration in the values before surgery [1]. Chi square method and ANOVA were in use for the comparison of the participants of all three groups.

RESULTS:

Patients & traits of varicocele were not much different in the participants of all three groups as presented in Table-1. No patient in all three groups stated intra-operative complications. The duration of the surgery was longer in the microscopy group as compared to the other groups for unilateral & bilateral varicoceles. The duration of the surgery in other two groups was much lower as mentioned in Table-2. There were comparable after surgery complications like infection of wound, scrotal hematoma & scrotal pain for long duration among the participants of all three groups (Table-2). Conservatives measures were in use for the treatment of the initial complications after surgery. The duration of recovery or time to go back to work was not much different in the patients of all three groups (Table-2).

Table 2. Operative and Postoperative Outcomes

Outcomes	Open			Laparoscopic			Microscopic			p Value
	Mean / No	± SD / %	Range	Mean / No	± SD / %	Range	Mean / No	± SD / %	Range	
Mean ± SD mins Operative Time (range)										
Unilat	46.0	17.0	(25-80)	34.0	10.0	(23-35)	62.0	17.0	(35-12)	<0.0010
Bilat	67.0	25.0	(30-120)	58.0	16.0	(35-950)	109.0	19.0	(65-140)	<0.0010
Mean ± SD days to return to work (range)	9.0	2.0	(7-15)	8.0	3.0	(5-14)	8.0	2.6	(7-10)	0.5000
Total	8/92	9.0		6/94	6.0		5/112	4.0		0.4700
Post-operative wound infection	2.0			0.0			2.0			
Post-operative scrotal hematoma	2.0			0.0			1.0			
Post-operative scrotal pain	4.0			6.0			2.0			
No. postoperative hydrocele	4/143	2.8		8/148	5.4		0/155			0.0200
No. recurrent varicocele	16/143	11		25/148	17		4/155	2.6		0.0010

The micro-surgical group was available with low prevalence of the recurring varicocele in comparison with the both other groups (Table-2). The occurrence of recurring varicocele in the group of laparoscopy was not much dissimilar than the patients available in open group (twenty-five out of 148 patients or 17.0% & sixteen out of 143 or 11.0%, correspondingly). The comparison between the parameters of semen after and before surgery displayed much improvement in the motility, morphology & concentration of the sperms (Table-3). The improvement magnitude in the count & motility of sperms was much high in the micro-surgical group as compared to other two groups (Table-3).

Table 3. Preoperative and Postoperative Semen Parameters

Semen Parameters		Preoperative		Postoperative		p Value
		Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Open	Sperm concentration million/ml)	22.0	5.20	33.0	6.30	0.0200
	Motility	22.0	2.60	31.0	2.10	0.0400
	Abnormal forms	65.0	2.20	50.0	2.90	0.0400
Laparoscopic	Sperm concentration million/ml)	23.0	4.30	38.0	5.50	0.0200
	Motility	21.0	2.80	30.0	3.20	0.0000
	Abnormal forms	70.0	3.40	55.0	2.90	0.0010
Microscopic	Sperm concentration million/ml)	17.0	4.90	40.0	6.20	<0.0010
	Motility	20.0	2.50	34.0	3.50	<0.0010
	Abnormal forms	61.0	2.80	56.0	3.10	0.0400

The amount of the patients who displayed advancement in the count & motility of sperms was much high in the group of micro-surgery & amount of the patients who displayed advancement in morphology of sperms was much comparable in patients of all three groups (Table-4). The rate of pregnancy at 1st year was not much dissimilar in all three groups. The rate of pregnancy was 33.0%, 31% & 38.0% in laparoscopic, open & micro-surgical groups correspondingly.

Table 4. Patients with Improved Semen Parameters

Improved Semen Parameters		Improved		Stable		Deteriorated	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Open	Count	56.0	61.00	13.0	14.00	23.0	25.00
	Motility	48.0	52.00	7.0	8.00	37.0	40.00
	Morphology	53.0	57.00	21.0	23.00	18.0	20.00
Laparoscopic	Count	50.0	54.00	6.0	6.00	36.0	40.00
	Motility	62.0	66.00	18.0	19.00	14.0	15.00
	Morphology	64.0	68.00	14.0	15.00	16.0	17.00
Microscopic	Count	92.0	82.00	9.0	8.00	11.0	10.00
	Motility	82.0	74.00	6.0	5.00	24.0	21.00
	Morphology	66.0	60.00	24.0	21.00	22.0	19.00

DISCUSSION:

There were two hundred and ninety-eight patients who underwent three different procedures of open, laparoscopic & micro-surgery for the treatment of the varicocele. The patients available with the palpable varicoceles were only the part of this research work. The formation of the hydrocele & recurring of varicocele were very common complications in most of the procedures. Similar to this research work, Cayman reviewed the experience of past works with repair of varicocele in adolescent and concluded no prevalence of the hydrocele underwent micro-surgical varicocelectomy in comparison with the 2.90% rate when other method of loupe magnification was in use & 5.90% frequency without magnification [8]. Watanabe also compared the effectualness of some methods in his research work [13]. Szabo & Kessler stated that lymphatic impediment was the reason of the formation of the hydrocele [15].

Some research works have displayed that artery of the semen could be ligated with no influence on the supply of blood to testes if there were spared arteries of the cremaster & vas deferens [16]. Some other case works showed that negative alterations in the quality of semen & testicular atrophy were present following the ligation of artery of sperms [17]. Current research work has displayed that there was advantage of laparoscopic technique of the less duration for surgery. Different research work has displayed the improved parameters of semen in the patients who underwent varicocelectomy [8, 12, 18]. But some research works have not concluded any advantageous impact [19]. We concluded the improvement in the parameters of semen in one hundred and eighty-two patients out of 298 (61.0%) who underwent different techniques of

varicocelectomy. This frequency was available with an agreement with 51.0% to 79.0% rates in the research works of the past [8, 12, 19, 20].

CONCLUSION:

The results of the research work concluded that micro-surgical varicocelectomy has much benefits over other two techniques like no formation of the hydrocele, a very low occurrence of the recurring of varicocele as well as good improvement in the count & motility of the sperms.

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